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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION A NOVEL HERBAL BASED FACE WASH BY USING HYDNORAAFRIANA (SUB FAMILY-HYDNORACEAE) FRUIT EXTRACT

Shibanjan Paul Roy

Freelancer Scientist, M.Pharm (Pharmacology)

Race Course Para, Jalpaiguri, Pin-735101, West Bengal, India

Email ID: shibanjan90@gmail.com

Abstract- There are many herbal based face wash invented. But in this research Hydнора Africana 2gm used for the external use for the treatment of Acne. In this time Hydнора Africana fruit extract used for the purpose of skin treatment such as Acne. Actually for this research I got the two street dogs which has acne but in their skin properly shaved but too much acne available. The acne occurred in two street dogs in hairless areas. Before I did this research of Hydнора Africana root extracts and after research I known that it is used as anti-diarrhoeal agent and antimicrobial with anti-fungal. But in this invention I performed the research for watching that this face wash is effective for the treatment of acne or not.

Introduction-In every year many face wash invented for the treatment of acne. The face wash first invented in 1990. Before I invented about Hydнора Africana root extract that it is

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anti-diarrhoeal and antimicrobial with anti-fungal also. But in this present study for the preparation of facewash. In this facewashresearch I got chin acne affected 2street dogs by lab. Acne occurs in dog on the bottom of skin around the mouth, lower lips and chin sometimes in the hairless areas. As Hydnora Africana's fruit also effective that's fruit extract also use.

Materials and Ingredients-

AS by the lab Hydnora Africana will be collected with fruits. Leaf extract will be used but now fruit extract also left that's fruit extracts also use. Actually the Hydnora Africana collected from South Africa after it collected from Malbazar by lab. First the dried fruit extract 100gm will be collected. After 2gm of Hydnora Africana will be ready for the preparation.

The other ingredients are-

61.495ml of liquid Castile soap

61.495ml of chamomile tea

42.26ml of Honey

2gm of Hydnora Africana fruit extract

0.75ml of sweet almond oil

4drops of rose oil(essential oil) but it is optional

PROCEDURE-

-Pour some liquid of liquid Castile soap into clean container. First we need a 61.495ml of liquid Castile soap. But we must make sure that is unscented and uncoloured because our skin will be irritate by scents.

-After for the face wash preparation chamomile tea also added. Actually according my knowledge I know that chamomile tea has anti-inflammatory properties and can help to reduce the redness of skin. So, I took 61.495ml but before added it to the container let the tea cool.

-After I considered for adding some honey in my face wash preparation. For this time I want to be more moisturizing cleanser so, I use 42.26ml of Honey. But this time I make sure that it is must translucent sort and runny.

-After this time i mixed with 2gm hydнора africana fruit extract with I must needed 0.75ml of sweet almond oil but this time I collected it very hardly after i mixed it.

-This time I considered for adding essential oil as example of rose oil of 4drops because it but it is optional

-After I closed the container tightly and shake it for few minutes when everything is combined.

-After the face wash will be prepared.

-But I prepared it 2times 1st all ingredients with rose oil and without rose oil for the testing of the herbal based face wash.

As for identify I gave name to the formulations

1st formulation name- Laxtanukanhai(with rose oil)

2nd formulation name-Rajkissurjchandbika(without rose oil)

Solubility Test- as adding solute for solubility analysis in small incremental amount to fixed the volume of solvents such as ethanol, acetone and chloroform. After undissolved particles will be examined.

PH Value- As the rules PH value should between 5-6.9. In this invention I took 1gm of this facewashafter with distilled water 100ml this 1gm will be dissolved properly after placed for 2hour. After then dip the glass electrode into an herbal facewash. The PH value without rose oil showed 6.3 and with rose oil showed 6.5

Invitro Release-The herbal formulation Rajkissurjchandbika is released for 19days when it will be analyzed and other Laxtanukanhai is released for 18days when it will be analyzed.

ADR- This formulations when applied on the street dogs for many days, we founded it showed no skin irritation and founds to be effective.

Result and Discussion-

Actually in this research I used chamomile tea which is used for the treatment of redness in skin after I used honey which also moisturizing our skin. Then about *Hydnora Africana* that we know about this plant this is very effective and it is used for the treatment of acne. It is antimicrobial, antifungal and anti-diarrhoeal. The main point is that it is non-toxic and harmless. So, in future I think many Pharmaceutical company research about *Hydnora Africana*. As for identify I gave name to the formulations

1st formulation name- Rajkissurjchandbika (with rose oil)

2nd formulation name- Laxtanukanhai (without rose oil)

This process made me very easy for this research.

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